

Structural Studies of Cu(II) and Ni(II) Complexes with Physiologically Active Ligands

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Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of physiologically active coumarin derivative, 8-acetyl-4-methyl umbelliferone and its oxime, hydrazone and thiosemicarbazone derivatives have been synthesized in the pH range of 5.5-8.00. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, conductivity, IR and electronic spectra, magnetic moments and TGA. Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of 8-acetyl-4-methyl umbelliferone and its thiosemicarbazone have been found to possess polymeric structures with the oxygen of the lactone carbonyl participating in coordination, resulting in octahedral and square planar dispositions respectively. Physiological activities of ligands and their metal chelates have been evaluated by kymographic studies.

COUMARIN (2H-1-benzopyran-2-one) and its derivatives have been found to exhibit physiological activity and are also extensively used as analytical reagents¹⁻³. Metal complexes of coumarin derivatives with hydroxy, acetyl and phenyl azo substituents as coordinating centres have been widely studied⁴⁻⁶. Umbelliferone (7-hydroxy coumarin) known for its antibiotic, antifungal activities^{7,8} having substituents like amino and nitro at position-8 and methyl at position-4 has been investigated for complexing ability^{9,10}. 8-Acetyl-4-methyl umbelliferone has been found to exhibit anticoagulant and plant growth regulant property^{11,12}. In this communication we are reporting the synthesis and structural studies of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of 8-acetyl-4-methyl umbelliferone (AMU) and its oxime (AMUO), hydrazone (AMUH) and thiosemicarbazone (AMUT) derivatives (Figs. 1-4).

metal complexes of AMU, AMUO and AMUH is also being reported.

Experimental

Methods and materials: All the solvents and reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Magnetic susceptibility was obtained at room temperature by using Faraday technique. Infrared spectra ($4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on a high resolution Perkin-Elmer-577 IR spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Electronic (mull) spectra were recorded on a Varian Cary-17D instrument (200-700 nm). Conductance measurements were done on a Philips conductivity bridge (model No. 3201). Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents in the ligand and the complexes were estimated by microanalysis. The metal estimations were carried out following standard

Fig. 1
AMU

Fig. 2
AMUO

Fig. 3
AMUH

Fig. 3a
AMUH

Fig. 4
AMUT

It is interesting to note that in the complexes of AMU and AMUT, the oxygen of lactone carbonyl participates in coordination resulting in polymeric structures. Our observation regarding the behaviour of AMU with Cu(II) is entirely different from the reported one¹³. The kymographic study¹⁴ of the

procedures¹⁵. Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out in a manually operated thermo-balance.

Synthesis: 8-Acetyl-4-methyl umbelliferone has been prepared by earlier reported procedure^{16,17}. The Schiff bases of AMU have been obtained by the standard procedures¹⁸.

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A hot solution of metal chloride (0.01 mole) in methanol (50 ml) was added to the hot solution of the respective ligand (0.03 mole) in methanol (100 ml). The reactants were refluxed on steam bath for about 2 hr. The complexes separated out after adjusting the pH in the range of 5.5-8.00. The resulting products were filtered in hot condition, washed with methanol, petroleum ether and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are stable to air and moisture. They decompose at higher temperatures. The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents. Some of them are soluble sparingly in DMF, DMSO. The negligibly low values of molar conductance around 5-6 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ of these complexes in 1 × 10⁻³ M DMF solution suggest their non-electrolytic behaviour. Elemental analysis (Table 1) indicates metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 2 for Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of AMU, AMUH and AMUO and 1 : 1 in AMUT chelates. IR spectral data of the ligands and metal complexes are given in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA : CALCD. (FOUND) %

Compound	C	H	N	S	Metal
AMU(C ₁₁ O ₄ H ₁₀)	66.05 (65.5)	4.58 (4.5)	—	—	—
Cu(C ₁₁ O ₄ H ₉) ₂	57.88 (47.80)	4.02 (4.1)	—	—	12.77 (12.70)
Ni(C ₁₁ O ₄ H ₉) ₂	58.45 (58.51)	4.06 (4.1)	—	—	11.92 (11.89)
AMUH(C ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ H ₁₂)	62.06 (62.0)	5.17 (5.11)	12.06 (12.2)	—	—
Cu(C ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ H ₁₁) ₂	54.80 (54.7)	4.18 (4.1)	10.65 (10.55)	—	12.09 (11.92)
Ni(C ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ H ₁₁) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	51.73 (51.56)	4.67 (4.61)	10.06 (10.1)	—	10.54 (10.2)
AMUO(C ₁₂ O ₄ NH ₁₁)	61.80 (61.59)	4.29 (4.32)	6.01 (5.98)	—	—
Cu(C ₁₂ O ₄ NH ₁₀) ₂	54.59 (54.62)	3.79 (3.72)	5.31 (5.25)	—	12.04 (12.12)
Ni(C ₁₂ O ₄ NH ₁₀) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	51.54 (51.0)	4.29 (4.3)	5.01 (5.0)	—	10.51 (10.2)
AMUT(C ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ SH ₁₂)	53.60 (53.1)	4.57 (4.6)	14.43 (14.40)	—	—
Cu(C ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ SH ₁₂)	44.25 (44.1)	3.12 (3.10)	11.91 (11.79)	9.07 (8.98)	18.02 (17.92)
Ni(C ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ S ₁₁)	44.85 (44.4)	3.16 (3.21)	12.18 (12.20)	9.20 (9.18)	16.88 (16.5)

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LIGANDS AND THE METAL COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Compound	νOH	νNH ₂		ν(C—O) (lac)	ν(C=O) (ace)	ν(C=N)	ν(C—O)
		asy	sy				
AMU	—	—	—	1740 _(s)	1625 _(s)	—	1205 _(s)
Cu(II)AMU	—	—	—	1715 _(s)	1585 _(s)	—	1225 _(s)
Ni(II)AMU	—	—	—	1720 _(s)	1590 _(s)	—	1220 _(s)
AMUT	3350 _(m)	3250 _(s)	3150 _(s)	1720 _(s)	—	1600 _(s)	1220 _(s)
Cu(II)AMUT	—	3250 _(s)	3150 _(s)	1700 _(s)	—	1575 _(s) & 1610 _(s)	1240 _(s)
Ni(II)AMUT	—	3250 _(s)	3150 _(s)	1705 _(s)	—	1580 _(s) & 1610 _(s)	1240 _(s)
AMUH	3220 _(m)	3350 _(s)	3250 _(s)	1700 _(s)	—	1600 _(s)	1230 _(s)
Cu(II)AMUH	—	3350 _(s)	3250 _(s)	1720 _(s)	—	1575 _(s)	1240 _(s)
Ni(II)AMUH	—	3350 _(s)	3250 _(s)	1720 _(s)	—	1580 _(s)	1240 _(s)
AMUO	3300–3200 _(s,b)	—	—	1720 _(s)	—	1600 _(s)	1230 _(s)
Cu(II)AMUO	3200 _(s)	—	—	1720 _(s)	—	1580 _(s)	1240 _(s)
Ni(II)AMUO	3100–3600 _(s,b)	—	—	1720 _(s)	—	1585 _(s)	1235 _(s)

s = strong ; m = medium ; b = broad.

Table 2. The magnetic and electronic spectral data are included in Table 3.

Complex	Electronic spectra (cm ⁻¹)	Magnetic data (B. M.)
Cu(II)AMU	13000–16000, 28600	2.00
Ni(II)AMU	15380, 20400, 23280, 28315	2.98
Cu(II)AMUT	16300, 18000, 20000	1.9
Ni(II)AMUT	20000	Diamagnetic
Cu(II)AMUH	16100, 18500, 20000	1.99
Ni(II)AMUH	16160, 20000, 21740	2.99
Cu(II)AMUO	18000–21000	1.8
Ni(II)AMUO	16666, 21280, 22220, 25000	3.1

Complexes of AMU: The ir spectrum of the ligand AMU does not show any band characteristic of hydroxyl group in 3600-2500 cm⁻¹ region, which is in accordance with the observation made by Sabata and Rout¹⁹. The absence of this band is attributed to strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding between 7-hydroxy and 8-acetyl group. A strong band observed at 1740 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to ν(C=O)²⁰ (lactone) and two bands at 1625 and 1205 cm⁻¹ to hydrogen bonded ν(C=O) acetyl and ν(C—O) phenolic respectively. A medium band at 1060 cm⁻¹ is characterized for ν_{asy}(C—O—C)²¹ corresponding to the cyclic ether grouping. In comparison with the ligand spectrum, the spectra of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes have shown downward shifts (35-40 cm⁻¹) in the ν(C=O) acetyl and upward shift (15-20 cm⁻¹) in the ν(C—O) phenolic groups indicating coordination through the acetyl oxygen and deprotonated phenolic oxygen respectively. An interesting feature observed is the red shift in ν(C=O) lactone to the extent of about 25 cm⁻¹, suggesting coordination through the lactone oxygen. This is further supported by downward shift in ν_{asy}(C—O—C) of the pyran ring. On the basis of ir data it is concluded that AMU behaves as a mono-basic ligand coordinating not only through phenolic and acetyl oxygen but also through lactone oxygen. New bands in the region of 370-460 and 360-480 cm⁻¹ in both the complexes are assignable to stretching frequencies of (M—O) and (M—N) bonds respectively²².

The magnetic moments for Cu(II) and Ni(II) AMU complexes were found to be 2.00 and 2.98 B.M. respectively at room temperature, showing the presence of one and two unpaired electrons. The electronic spectrum of Cu(II) complex shows a broad band in the region of 13000-16000 cm^{-1} and intense band at 28600 cm^{-1} . The first band can be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition, suggesting octahedral geometry²³ and the remaining band to charge transfer. Four electronic spectral bands have been observed at 28315, 23250, 20400 and 15380 cm^{-1} for Ni(II) complex. The first one being intense is attributed to charge transfer. The 15380 and 23250 cm^{-1} bands are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions²⁴. The weak band, observed at 20400 cm^{-1} is attributed to spin-forbidden transition between the triplet and singlet transition i.e., ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ ²⁵. These transitions are in accordance with octahedral geometry. In view of the insoluble nature and lactone carbonyl participation in coordination, polymeric structures with octahedral geometry have been proposed (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. AMU complexes, M = Cu(II) or Ni(II).

Complexes of AMUT : The ir spectrum of the ligand shows bands at 3350, 3250 and 3150 cm^{-1} which are assignable to $\nu(\text{OH})$ chelated, $\nu_{as\nu} \text{NH}_2$ and $\nu_{s\nu} \text{NH}_2$ respectively. The bands at 1720 and 1600 cm^{-1} are characterized for $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ lactone and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. A medium band at 1170 cm^{-1} is attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ ²⁶. The disappearance of the band due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ in complexes suggest deprotonation of phenolic group and subsequent bonding through this oxygen. There is a red shift in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ lactone by about 20 cm^{-1} in both the complexes indicating the participation of oxygen of lactone carbonyl in chelation. Another feature observed is the absence of the band due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and appearance of a new band at 1610 cm^{-1} characteristic of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. This indicates the conversion of the ligand from thione to thiol form during complex formation²⁷. The $\nu(\text{S}-\text{H})$, which generally appears in 2590-2450 cm^{-1} region²⁸ is absent in the complexes indicating deprotonation of -SH group and subsequent coordination through sulphur. In the spectrum of the complexes, a red shift is observed in the original $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. This is attributed to the binding of nitrogen of the original azomethine group. Thus it is concluded that ligand (AMUT) acts as dibasic tridentate.

Magnetic moment data show that Cu(II) complex is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.9$ B.M.) whereas Ni(II) complex is diamagnetic. Three electronic spectral bands at 20000, 18000, 16300 cm^{-1} are assignable to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transitions respectively²⁹, suggesting square planar geometry for Cu(II) complex. Diamagnetic nature of Ni(II) complex is consistent with square planar arrangement³⁰ (Fig. 6). It is further supported by an electronic spectral band at 20000 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition³¹.

Fig. 6. AMUT complexes, M = Cu(II) or Ni(II).

Complexes of AMUH : The ir spectra of the ligand show bands at 3350, 3250 and 3220 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{as\nu} \text{NH}_2$, $\nu_{s\nu} \text{NH}_2$ and νOH chelated. The bands at 1700, 1600 and 1230 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ lactone, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenolic respectively. In metal chelates, the disappearance of the band due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ and blue shift in $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ confirm the deprotonation of phenolic -OH group and complexation through oxygen. There is no change in the νNH_2 bands indicating its non-involvement in coordination. The bathochromic shift in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (20 cm^{-1}) indicates coordination through azomethine nitrogen. In contrast to AMU complexes a hypsochromic shift has been observed in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ lactone. The probable explanation in this case may be that the resonance participation of the electron pair on oxygen reported in similar compounds³² (Fig. 3a) is diminished by the substitution of metal ion in place of hydrogen atom which will result in increasing double bond character between lactone oxygen and carbon and hence the hypsochromic shift and the non-participation of oxygen of lactone carbonyl in coordination. A broad trough in the region of 3380-3450 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 850 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of coordinated water in Ni(II) complex³³. Thermogravimetric analysis reveals weight loss equivalent to two water molecules per mole of the Ni(II) complex at $\sim 140^\circ$. A few weak absorptions observed at 490 and 520 cm^{-1} , 485 and 520 cm^{-1} for Cu(II) and Ni(II) complex are attributed to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ ³².

The observed magnetic moment value for the Cu(II) complex is 1.99 B.M. The electronic spectrum shows three bands at 16100, 18500 and 20000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions²⁹ respectively indicating square planar geometry. (Fig. 7).

The Ni(II) complex shows magnetic moment value of 2.9 B.M. which is in the range expected for octahedral complexes. The electronic spectrum shows three bands at 16160, 20000 and 21740 cm^{-1} . The first two are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition²⁴. The last weak band observed at 20000 cm^{-1} is assignable to spin-forbidden ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition²⁵. On the basis of above observations Ni(II) complex is assigned octahedral geometry (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. AMUH complexes.

Fig. 8. AMUH complexes.

Complexes of AMUO: The broad bands at 3300-3200 cm^{-1} and the strong bands at 1700, 1600, 1230 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of the ligand are assigned to hydrogen bonded -OH stretchings of phenol and oxime groups, $\nu(C=O)$ lactone, $\nu(C=N)$, $\nu(C-O)$ phenolic respectively. Cu(II) complex shows a strong band at 3200 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(-OH)$ oxime, involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding²⁴. A broad trough in case of Ni(II) complex in the region of 3100-3400 cm^{-1} is attributed to the presence of coordinated water which is supported by a band of medium intensity around 940 cm^{-1} ²³. Thermogravimetric analysis confirms the presence of two water molecules per mole of Ni(II) complex. In both the complexes there is a downward shift of $\nu(C=N)$ (15-20 cm^{-1}) indicating participation of azomethine nitrogen in bonding. An upward shift observed in case of $\nu(C-O)$ phenolic suggest coordination through this oxygen. The blue shift in $\nu(C=O)$ lactone in both the complexes can be explained on the same line as described earlier in AMUH complexes.

The observed magnetic moments are 1.8 B.M. and 3.1 B.M. for Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes respectively. The electronic spectral bands in the range of 18000-21000 cm^{-1} in Cu(II) complex and

16000-25000 cm^{-1} in Ni(II) complex are indicative of square planar and octahedral geometries respectively (Figs. 9 and 10).

Fig. 9. AMUO complexes.

Fig. 10. AMUO complexes.

Physiological study: Frog's heart was isolated by opening the thoracic cavity from a doubly pithed frog. Ringer solution which is isoosmotic and isotonic was used for perfusion studies in the isolated heart. Glucose was added to the ringer as an energy supplement. Heart beat and the rhythm were recorded on a smoked cylinder attached to kymograph drum moving at a slow speed (1.5 rpm), following the reported procedure¹⁴. Aqueous solutions of the metal chlorides and the ligands of 10 ppm concentration at pH 7.4 were used to study the effects on the isolated heart. The ligand solutions followed by solution mixtures

Fig. 11. N - Normal, H - AMUH, O - AMUO, A - AMU
Kymograms

containing the metal and ligand in appropriate proportions for complex formation, were introduced into the heart, along with the perfusion fluid. At the end of each test the heart was allowed to return to normal speed and rhythm by allowing pure ringer solution to perfuse through the heart. The time taken by the heart to return to the normal rhythm and speed however varied from ligand to ligand and also from complex to complex. In general the Cu(II) complexes did not exert changes in the systolic beat while Ni(II) complexes appeared to have altered the systolic beat more than the diastolic beat. Ligands in general accelerated speed while their complexes increased the rhythm further. The relevant kymograms are given in Fig. 11. This type of work was reported in case of some substituted coumarins on perfused rabbit heart²⁵. Studies are in progress regarding the anticoagulant properties of these complexes.

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